

CURRICULUM ENRICHMENT FOR LEARNING OUTCOMES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract:

In higher education learning outcomes are the specifications of what a student should learn and demonstrate on successful completion of the course or the programme. It could be seen as desired outcome of learning process more importantly in terms of acquisition of skills and knowledge. The ultimate learning outcome may be reflected in the vision and mission of the institution like for example, developing younger generation into responsible citizens of the country with social sensitivity and general neutrality upholding values while at the same time employable and successful in their career. Institutional strategy to nurture critical thinking, creativity and scientific temper among the students and transform them into life long learners and innovators. Learner-centered education through appropriate methodologies facilitates effective learning as teaching-learning modalities of higher education are considered to be relevant to the learner group. Curriculum delivery and pedagogy should incorporate multitude of learning experiences such as project based learning, lab. Based learning, activity based learning, experiential learning, field based learning, technology based learning, community based learning, team based learning, analytical learning, observation based learning, social service based learning etc. The role of the institution is to identify and provide such experiences as to improve their learning through the all-round learning opportunities available to them. This paper discusses the efforts of a higher education institution to devise a variety of curriculum enrichments in learning to promote student learning outcomes.

Index Terms: Learning Outcome, Curriculum Enrichment & Learner-Centered Education

Introduction:

Curriculum delivery and pedagogy should incorporate multitude of learning experiences so that desired outcome of learning process through acquisition of skills and knowledge will result in critical thinking, creativity and scientific temper among the students and transform them into life long learners and innovators. This is also essential for developing younger generation into responsible citizens of the country with social sensitivity and general neutrality upholding values while at the same time employable and successful in their career. Various enrichment measures are employed such as project based learning, lab. Based learning, activity based learning, experiential learning, field based learning, technology based learning, community based learning, team based learning, analytical learning, observation based learning, social service based learning etc.

Institutions goals and objectives are focused on enhancing knowledge, skills and readiness to be absorbed in the job market. By keeping this in mind, the institution supplements the curriculum by variety of means:

- ✓ Curriculum delivery & pedagogy
- ✓ Skill development Package
- ✓ Exposure visits
- ✓ Certification Programmes
- ✓ Workshops
- ✓ Employability Trainings

- ✓ Industry-Institution Interface Programmes
- ✓ Field Visits
- ✓ Seminars & Conferences
- ✓ Guest Lectures
- ✓ Video Lecture
- ✓ Value Addition Classes
- ✓ Imparting Messages Celebration of National/International Days
- ✓ Encouragement to take up online Programs offered by accredited Universities.

Curriculum Delivery & Pedagogy:

The curriculum is effectively delivered through the following:

- ✓ Topic based assignments
- ✓ Student presentations
- ✓ Case study analysis
- ✓ Student feedback
- ✓ Research Projects
- ✓ Field Practicum
- ✓ Laboratory based Practicals
- ✓ Thematic Fest
- ✓ Forum Activities

Skill Development Package:

The following skill development programmes are offered as a package as part and parcel with the curriculum:

- ✓ Fund Raising
- ✓ Innovative ideas in Marketing
- ✓ Business Communication
- ✓ Effective Presentation
- ✓ Problem solving
- ✓ Team Building
- ✓ Entrepreneurship & Small business Planning
- ✓ Application software development Skill
- ✓ Website development & Design Skill
- ✓ Fund Raising Skill
- ✓ Team Presentation Skill
- ✓ Troubleshooting Skills
- ✓ Android Application Development Skills
- ✓ Business Correspondence
- ✓ Spoken English
- ✓ Public speaking
- ✓ Program organizing
- ✓ Personality Building
- ✓ Time Management
- ✓ Communication Skills
- ✓ Leadership Skills
- ✓ Human Relationship Skills
- ✓ Soft Skills

Exposure Visits:

The college provides opportunity for exposure visit to gain first-hand knowledge. Some of them are:

- ✓ Orientation programmes

- ✓ Industry visits
- ✓ Study tours
- ✓ International educational visits
- ✓ Student exchange programmes

Certification Programmes:

Various certificate programmes bridge the gap between curriculum and industry requirements. Some of the certificate programmes are listed below:

1. Management and Commerce:

- ✓ Certificate course in Online Investment
- ✓ Certificate course on quantitative analysis using MATLAB/OCTAVE
- ✓ Certificate course on Investment Banking
- ✓ Certificate course in Cloud computing
- ✓ Certificate course in Android Mobile Applications
- ✓ Certificate course in Retail Marketing & Brand Management
- ✓ Certificate course in SPSS /PSPY statistical software
- ✓ Certificate Course in Computer Application (Tally, Excel, & Access)
- ✓ Certificate Course in R-Statistical Computing for Business Analytics
- ✓ Certificate Course in Blue Ocean Strategy and Green Business
- ✓ Certificate Course in Animation & Visual Effects
- ✓ Certificate Course on Mobile Business & Mobile banking

2. Information Technology:

- ✓ Certificate course in Animation & Visual Effects
- ✓ Certificate course in Strategic management in IT Sector
- ✓ Certificate course in Enterprises Resource Planning
- ✓ Certificate course in Entrepreneurial Development Programme
- ✓ Certificate course in R – Statistical Computing & Graphics for Business Analytics
- ✓ Certificate course in Cyber Law & IT security

3. Social Sciences:

- ✓ Certificate course in HRD
- ✓ Certificate course in Counseling
- ✓ Certificate course in Human Rights
- ✓ Certificate course in NGO Management
- ✓ Certificate course in Industrial & Labour Laws

4. Workshops:

Workshops of varying duration for all the courses are organized. This will supplement the curriculum gap with the institutions goals and objectives. A list of such workshops is listed below.

5. Management and Commerce:

- ✓ Workshop for preparing ICWA Aspirants
- ✓ Workshop on Corporate Yoga & Mind Control
- ✓ Workshop on Business Etiquettes
- ✓ Workshop on Nanotechnology Commercialization & Business Opportunities
- ✓ Workshop on Disaster Management
- ✓ Workshop on ERP Modules Applications & Vendors
- ✓ Workshop on Mobile Business & Mobile Banking

6. Computer and Information Technology:

- ✓ Workshop in Android Operating System & Application Development
- ✓ Workshop on PHP and MySQL
- ✓ Workshop on Stress Management

- ✓ Workshop on Cloud Computing
- ✓ Workshop on E-Business website development
- ✓ Workshop on Quantitative Analysis using MATLAB/OCTAVE

7. Social Science:

- ✓ Workshop on Book Review Techniques
- ✓ Workshop on Essay Writing Practice
- ✓ Workshop on Gender sensitization
- ✓ Workshop on News Clippings Analysis & Integration
- ✓ Workshop for Character & Spiritual Development

Employability Trainings:

- ✓ Competitive exam training
- ✓ Interview preparedness
- ✓ Effective Decision making
- ✓ SWOT Analysis
- ✓ Oral & Written Communication
- ✓ Problem Solving
- ✓ Work Ethics

Industry-Institution Interface Programmes:

Various programmes are planned, implemented and promoted for Industry-Institution Interface.

- ✓ Industry Projects
- ✓ Guest lectures by Industry Experts
- ✓ Campus Recruitment
- ✓ Summer Placement
- ✓ Block Placement
- ✓ Mentorship Programs by Industry Managers
- ✓ Round Table Interaction with Entrepreneurs & Industry Experts
- ✓ Stories of Successful Entrepreneurs
- ✓ Development of Industry related Business cases
- ✓ Consultancy services

Field Visits:

- ✓ Orientation Visits
- ✓ Community Surveys
- ✓ Regular Field Practicum
- ✓ Social service activities

Video Lectures: Video lectures on Business Management, Social Science and Computer & IT are shown to the students periodically to enrich and supplement the Curriculum.

Value Addition Classes: Each theory paper adds extra chapter towards the end, focusing on value building which is beyond the limits of curriculum offered by the University.

Imparting Messages by Celebration of National/International Days: Days such as International Water Day, Health Day, Mothers day, Environment day, Human Rights day, Climate day etc. are observed through conducting talks & community awareness processions.

Encouragement to Take Up Online University Programs: Free video online courses from accredited Universities in India or abroad are encouraged in order to enhance the global competencies of the students and faculty.

Mobile Education: The College takes the faculty to the community/ industry as a part of learning through mobile education. Some of the Faculty Development Programs are

conducted outside the college to enhance the effectiveness of training.

Blended Learning: In addition to chalk and talk method of teaching, the faculty members are using the IT enabled learning tools such as PPT, Video clippings, Audio system, online sources, Simulation software, communication lab and decision making games and field work conference to expose the students to combine advanced knowledge with practical learning. The following efforts are adopted by the institution to modify, enrich and organize the curriculum to enhance the experience of the students with needs of the dynamic employment market.

Case Study Development: Students are given opportunity to extract real life context from organizations where they visit either for field practicum of research project work or summer placement and these are worked out into case studies through group exercises under the guidance of the faculty supervisors. This enables to enrich and organize the curriculum beyond routine classroom learning through lecture, and improve the dynamism and competitiveness of the students in the employment market.

Group Discussions: Topics of monotonous nature are divided to be discussed among students in groups and generate ideas in line with their experience and viewpoints. These discussions are guided by the faculty to retain the curriculum relevance. Ultimately, group presentations lead to encouragement of students initiatives and leadership qualities which are the focus in the employment markets.

Simulation: Efforts are made to utilize simulation techniques to reproduce real life situations in classroom. Students develop ability for positive responses in problem solving and decision making.

Laboratory Based Learning: Students are encouraged to utilize various Application software in computer laboratory. They are also trained to develop reports using various statistical analysis and data management & interpretation packages through network based learning.

Field Work Based Learning: Fieldwork has the potential to enrich the curriculum combining the experiences of the students with concept based theoretical learning.

Exposure Based Learning: Through study tour, industry visits and interaction with resource persons. exposure based learning will provide the techniques of resource mobilization, quality production, marketing strategies, customer satisfaction and Human resource management in business.

Research Based Learning: Undertaking research projects as part of course requirement enables students with adequate know-how on application of alternative solutions to social context.

Experiential Learning: Brand programs are organized as a regular feature involving students giving them insights and providing them opportunity for experiential learning.

Student Forum Based Activities : Various student forums like HR Forum, Marketing Forum, Finance Forum, IT Forum are also providing opportunity for students to creatively reflect their experiences and integrating with it curriculum.

Entrepreneurship Development Cell: A separate cell for entrepreneurship development is incorporated in the college. This cell creates awareness of need and relevance of entrepreneurship as career option among the students thereby strengthening their Entrepreneurship skills.

Team Work Activities: Students of the College plan and organize various social programs like Teachers Day Celebration, Onam Celebration, Iftar Party, Karnataka Rajyothsava etc.

Idea Creation through Marketing Exhibition: MBA, BBM and B.Com students involve in creating new business models/Ideas in Teams of 4-5 students and present their

model in Marketing Exhibition conducted by the respective Departments. This kind of practical learning through Idea creation leads to innovation in business models/marketing Ideas. Resources and technology are extended to students to support learning. The following is a list of such facilities.

- ✓ **LCD Projectors in Each Class:** All the classrooms are fitted with LCD projectors. Faculty members use power point presentations to make classroom teaching more effective.
- ✓ **Audio Visual Aids:** Audio Visual Aids are available in all the classrooms. Faculties are using video case studies, Movie clippings on management concepts, short films, and advertisements to explain certain topics more effectively.
- ✓ **WI-fi Campus:** The campus is WI-fi enabled and has high Speed internet connectivity all the time. The faculty members are using internet facility to show real time information on industry, market and economy to the students in the class rooms.
- ✓ **Computer Labs:** Computer labs used to make students to work on applications or internet for sourcing information.
- ✓ **TV:** Television is installed in the college. Channels like Business news are played during the working hours. This will help the students to update themselves on the issues.
- ✓ **Digital Library:** The faculty gives assignments, which would require students to use the digital library. The digital library enables the students to get research reports, case studies and any other relevant information required to complete the given assignments.
- ✓ **Public Address System:** The classrooms & Auditorium are equipped with the public address system. Each classroom has a hand mike, collar mike and speakers. This helps the students and faculty members in their presentations, events like subject quiz and interactions in the classroom.
- ✓ **Surveillance Camera based Monitoring in the Campus:** The centralized surveillance facility through fixed cameras in all classrooms give real time as well as recorded discipline in the class which helps monitoring for effective teaching.
- ✓ **Internet Based Library Services:** The faculty members can avail various internet based library services such as accessing various journals, Industry and research databases, other services from Delnet, EBSCO, etc. and internal library resource facilities which are linked to the institutional website.
- ✓ **National Mission on Education through Information and Communication Technology (NME-ICT):** The faculty members are also availing information and services provided by National Mission on Education through Information and Communication Technology to prepare their study materials, lectures, and for advanced information.
- ✓ **High Speed Printers & Scanners Facility:** Although sparingly used, the high speed printers and scanners are help the faculty to prepare multiple copies of case studies, business game etc.
- ✓ **NPTEL Video Lectures:** The College is encouraging to watch NPTEL video lecturers of IIT professors in the area of Computer Science, Business Management and social Science by downloading such videos and issuing the CD's of such lectures by College library.
- ✓ **Virtual Lab:** Through simulation in virtual lab, e-learning is enhanced.
- ✓ **Digital Camera & Videography Facility:** Through digital videography the classroom presentations are replayed to serve as feedback for improved learning.

✓ **Open Educational Resources:**

- Training of usage of Open Courseware by MIT & Sloan School of Business, IIM's, IIT's, IISC & IIIT's.
- Training & usage of Open Source Software from AICTE websites.
- Training on finding & usage of case studies from various free sources.
- Training on online Job hunting through online job service providers.
- Training on finding & usage of online text books from various websites.
- Training on finding & usage of edX consortium online courses

(A) Academic Support:

- ✓ Academic Support through predesigned study materials benefit all the students undergoing various courses in the college.
- ✓ Academic Support through Mentoring is provided to weak students in respective subjects by the concerned faculty and a record of the progress is maintained for continuous monitoring.
- ✓ Academic Advice through Course Co-ordinator every week helps to unwind student pressure from curriculum demands.

(B) Personal Support:

- ✓ Individual Monitoring focus on erratic behavior in the classroom or college premises.
- ✓ Health guidance is provided by Campus medical Officer
- ✓ Financial support through Bank Loan is arranged.
- ✓ Job opportunities are intimated and assisted to seek Placement
- ✓ Attendance shortage and continued absence is intimated periodically to home/parents through SMS.

(C) Psycho-Social Support:

Psycho-social support is provided to the students through Counseling. The various teaching –learning methods adopted in the Institute to enhance the competency of the students for better learning outcomes are listed as follows.

- ✓ **Project Based Teaching:** Faculty members give minor projects to group of students in different courses. On the completion of the projects, the team has to present the same and the faculty will award suitable marks/grades.
- ✓ **Lab Based Teaching:** The Institute also has three computer labs with internet facility. The students are taken to the lab by the faculty members to provide them real time information on subjects.
- ✓ **Experiential Learning:** To improve the understanding of the subject case studies are framed jointly by faculty and students recalling their experience during visits and observations. This includes managerial styles, superior and subordinate relationship, interpersonal communication, problem solving etc. For this purpose the students are sent on short-term assignments to the industry to have practical experience on working of industry.
- ✓ **Theater Based Learning:** The students are required to enact / explain certain concept through theater performance like role play, drama or short play on the assigned topics. Street plays are enacted in public locations to create awareness on social issues.
- ✓ **Simulation Games:** To give a real time experience of the business problems, simulation games are played in the classrooms. Students get a real feel of decision making, problem analysis and problem solving.
- ✓ **Video Case Study:** Faculties assigned students with special projects like making

video case studies on specific topics.

- ✓ **Activity Based Learning:** Students are involved in various activities and management games related to the topics from the subject.
- ✓ **Technology Based Learning:** The internet, LCD, different application software etc. enable technology based learning.
- ✓ **Learning from Nature & Environment:** Rural camp conducted for the students of social work and National Service Scheme are meant to learn from nature and environment.
- ✓ **Community Based Learning:** Various activities conducted in the communities for MSW students and the activities conducted by the College NGO by name SIRRA provides community based learning.
- ✓ **Field Work Based Learning:** MSW course require specific number of field work practicum as part of the curriculum. This is meant to sensitize the social work students to social issues.
- ✓ **Analytical Learning:** Quantitative techniques of analysis are used in learning mostly by MCA students and also by finance specialization students of MBA.
- ✓ **Team Based Learning:** The sum of individual performance is always less than teams' performance. Hence in software development team based learning is made use of.
- ✓ **Observation Based Learning:** Demonstrations such as role play facilitates observation based learning.
- ✓ **Social Service Based Learning:** Community interactions help, build and develop interpersonal relationship through which social service is channelized.
- ✓ **Simulated Learning through Digital Library:** MBA Students are exposed to the stock market operations and trading through simulated online games available with the digital library of the college.
- ✓ **Library based research work:** Students are exposed to various sources of online information and instructed to carry out the fundamental and technical analysis practically.

Conclusion:

The objective of higher education is to prepare the students for a career which gives them self fulfillment while at the same time provides the nation with responsible citizens who have social sensitivity, gender neutrality and upholding values of equality and mutual respect. The curriculum delivery should take into account the needs and wishes of the aspirants as well as interest and pace of learning. Pedagogy has to be reoriented to accommodate innovative curriculum enrichment measures. A large number of measures are suggested here which will serve to enhance learning outcomes and transform higher education institutions into centres of advanced learning.

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